

THE FACTORS INFLUENCING THE INTENTION TO USE INTERNET BANKING: A STUDY OF UNDERGRADUATES IN SRI LANKA

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Introduction

In the past decades, information systems and information technology developed rapidly. Due to this, every sector in Sri Lanka tries to implement new technical development for their organizations, particularly in the banking industry. Internet banking is becoming more and more common. (Suraweera, 2011). The customer's intention for internet banking was influenced by several factors. Some of these include perceived utility, perceived usefulness, perceived security, attitude, subjective norms, domestic variables, perceived behavioural control, and trust (Bruce Mwiya, 2017). Some of these elements have a greater impact on the intention to use internet banking. Some factors depend on other factors.

There are several types of research conducted in many countries to identify the factors influencing the intention to use internet banking (Ching Mun Cheah, 2011) (Benjamin B. Angenu, 2015) (Lufwendo Lishomwa, 2020) (Maitlo GM, 2015). Research was done to determine the factors influencing people's intentions to utilize internet banking in Sri Lanka as well.. (Aluthge DN, 2017) (Suraweera, 2011) (Perera, The Factors Influencing On the Customer Adoption of Internet Banking System Special Reference to the

Sampath Bank in Colombo District, February 2018) (HETTIARACHCHI, 2017) (Krishnapillai, 2020).

But still, there are differences between identified factors in different research papers. The factors influencing the intention to use internet banking still need to be investigated thoroughly as there is a research gap. Apparently, there is a need to identify the most important factors influencing the intention to use internet banking with special reference to the undergraduate of Sri Lanka.

There are some factors that influence the adoption of internet banking perspectives among undergraduates in Sri Lanka. The purpose of this study is to investigate the factors which are affecting the adoption of internet banking and examine the effect of those identified factors on the intention to use internet banking among undergraduates in Sri Lanka.

Methodology

The conceptual framework is developed using three well established theories Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and Theory of planned behaviour (TPB), and a construct to measure the effect of Internet banking website features on the intention to use Internet banking.

The hypotheses of the studies are,

- There is a positive effect of Perceived usefulness on Attitude towards internet banking. (Bruce Mwiya, 2017), (Krishnapillai, 2020).

- There is a positive effect of Perceived ease of use on Attitude towards internet banking. (Nawaz, 2016).
- There is a positive effect of Trust on Attitude towards internet banking (Bruce Mwiya, 2017).
- There is a positive effect of the attitude toward internet banking on the intention to use of internet banking services (Bruce Mwiya, 2017).
- There is a positive effect of the intention to use of internet banking services on the actual use of internet banking.

The target interest of this study was undergraduates studying at the Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce of the University of Sri Jayawardenepura. A survey questionnaire was designed as the instrument of the study to collect the data. Likert scale from strongly disagree to strongly agree (1-5) was applied in the questionnaire to evaluate responses.

Descriptive analysis and multivariate statistical analysis are the two data analysis methods chosen to do the data analysis.

Results and Discussion

First research objective was to identify the factors influencing the intention to use internet banking among undergraduates in Sri Lanka. This is addressed using comprehensive literature review. this perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, trust, attitude was selected for this research.

Second research objective was to examine the effects of those identified factors on the intention to use internet banking among undergraduates in Sri Lanka. This is achieved through Hypothesis development and analysis. Three out of five hypotheses of the study were supported according to the results of the Path model analysis. The path coefficient values (β) were utilized to ascertain the cause-effect relationship (see Table 6). Path coefficient values describe the direct effects of an independent variable on a dependent variable in the path model (Jodie B. Ullman, 2012).

Table 2 Result of structural model analysis

	Hypothesis	Path Coefficient	T Statistics	p Value
H1	Perceived usefulness ->Attitude towards internet banking	0.165	1.252	0.211
H2	Perceived ease of use -> Attitude towards internet banking	0.407	2.401	0.109
H3	Trust -> Attitude towards internet banking	0.226	1.602	0.017

H4	Attitude towards internet banking -> intention to use internet banking	0.511	4.873	0.000
H5	intention to use internet banking -> Actual use of internet banking	0.560	5.645	0.000

**Significance at $p < 0.05$*

H1 Perceived usefulness has a positive effect on Attitude towards internet banking. However, due to the non-significance of perceived usefulness ($\beta=0.165$, $p=0.211$), H1 was not supported. H2 suggested that Perceived ease of use has a positive effect on Attitude towards internet banking. Due to the non-significance of attitude ($\beta=0.407$, $p=0.109$), H2 was also not supported. H3 Trust ($\beta=0.226$, $p=0.017$) is also found statistically significant and has a positive effect on Attitude towards internet banking. H4 Attitude towards internet banking ($\beta=0.511$, $p=0.000$) is also found statistically significant and has a positive effect on intention to use internet banking. H5 intention to use internet banking ($\beta=0.560$, $p=0.000$) is also found statistically significant and has a positive effect on Actual use of internet banking.

Conclusion

The purpose of this research was to explore the influencing factors of internet banking practices evidenced by Sri Lanka undergraduates. The research model was an illustration based upon TPB (Theory of planned behaviour), TAM (Technology Acceptance Model). A Questionnaire survey was conducted to gather the data and responses were gathered from random banking customers who were internet bank users from Sri Lanka

undergraduates. The first purpose of the research was to identify the factors influencing the intention to use internet banking among undergraduates, perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, trust, and attitude were identified as the factors. Second purpose of the research was to identify the effect of those identified factors on intention to use internet banking among undergraduates. Perceived ease of use was identified as the factor that positively effect on the attitude towards internet banking, Attitude also significantly impacts on the intention to use of internet banking and intention to use positively effect on actual use of internet banking. The study was conducted to explore the factors influence the intention to use internet banking. As a result, there were significant findings made compared to other previous research; it has identified that, usefulness is the most important factor that impacts the attitude toward internet banking whereas some others identified trust and perceived ease of use. All are important factors that have a positive impact on internet banking. However, this research signifies that ease of use as the factor that positively affects attitude towards internet banking and also attitude positively effects on intention to use internet banking. Accordingly, undergraduates are thinking about the ease of use on attitude towards internet banking and intended behaviour effected by attitude towards internet banking actual behaviour effected by intended behaviour.

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